

Compatible authentication and key agreement protocol for low power and lossy network in IoT environment

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Abstract

Today, the Internet of Things can be described as the fastest-growing network that offers applications in a wide range of applications. This breadth has led to a wide range of IoT research. Applications of this network can be mentioned in various sectors such as e-health, smart homes, smart cities, and everything in smart cities via the Internet, where the collection and exchange of large amounts of data is undeniable. The IoT also supports large-scale low-power networks (LLNs) and uses the RPL protocol to route low-power, low-resource nodes on this large scale. Due to the exchange of sensitive data in this network, security is a critical issue. However, RPLs have many serious vulnerabilities, including the use of symmetric encryption that attackers can exploit. In addition, the privacy and security of network nodes are other challenges of this network. Therefore, there is a significant need for an effective and secure authentication scheme that enables IoT users to authenticate each other and share the session key to a secure meeting. In this paper, we aim to provide a secure protocol to enhance the security of the RPL protocol against a variety of network attacks. For this purpose, a key agreement protocol and authentication mechanism using ECC theory are proposed. Finally, we show that the proposed scheme is secure against routine network attacks and incurs a small computational and communication cost that is compatible with nodes with limited resources.

Keywords : RPL , IoT , Security , Privacy , Key agreement , Authentication , ECC

I. Introduction

In recent years, a new era has emerged in Internet networks called the Internet of Things (IoT) [1-2]. It is noteworthy that the Internet of Things has become extremely important, and its efficiency in connecting the billions of objects used has led to its expansion around the world [3-4]. The advent of the Internet of Things has led to the emergence of a particular category of networks that can be known as low power networks and loss networks (LLN) [5-6]. LLNs can be used efficiently and practically in designing and manufacturing commercial devices for emerging markets. The Internet of Things includes the deployment of large-scale low-power networks (LLNs), including resource-limited devices such as sensors and RFIDs [7]. One of the challenges in LNNs is routing, which requires an effective routing protocol that meets the requirements of the program [8]. The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) proposed the 6LOWPAN Applicable Protocol for LLNs in the IoT environment [9]. One of the basic requirements for implementing and deploying LNNs on a large scale is routing in that infrastructure, and the protocols used for routing in WSN are not suitable for LNNs in an IoT network. Therefore, the IETF has provided a routing protocol for low power networks and loss (RPL) for LLNs in the Internet of Things. RPL is fully compatible with LLNs and supports all their traffic flow requirements in a wide range of applications [10]. The RPL routing protocol is based on IPv6 [11]. Restrictions on RPL-based networks cause network nodes to be exposed to a variety of security attacks [12]. In addition, RPL does not support security features and does not have the ability to provide complete security and routing security, thus making it vulnerable to all types of network attacks [13]. Even if encryption mechanisms are used for security, it can only prevent external attacks. When nodes in the network are compromised, they can become an internal enclosure within the network,

in which case encryption techniques alone will not be able to protect the network. Extensive studies have been conducted on IoT network security. Due to the fact that a large number of devices and network nodes use the RPL protocol, a huge range of network entities are exchanging important data. So, security in RPL becomes a very important issue that needs to be addressed significantly. Because in the routing process, the data that is being transmitted should not be accessed by an intruder or an unauthorized third party on the network or leaked out of the network. Although several security measures have been considered for the security of the RPL protocol, there are threats to the security of this protocol.

A. Concepts of cryptographic system:

1. Elliptical Curve Cryptography

Elliptic curve (ECC) cryptography is one of the modern techniques in the world of public-key cryptography and encryption, which is based on the elliptic curve theory. This asymmetric encryption mechanism can be used to create faster, smaller, and more efficient encryption keys. The ECC uses a mathematical process to merge two separate keys, and its output is used to encrypt and decrypt data. This asymmetric cryptography system uses an elliptical curve called E and a set of points with coordinates, $pf \in * pf \in () x, y$. The points along the graph are represented by the following equations:

$$Y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$$

Where $a, b \in \mathbb{F}_p$ and $4a^3 + 27b^2 \neq 0$

The elliptic curve cryptography system consists of the sum of points and point multiplication, which are the two main factors of this cryptographic mechanism. The point multiplication factor is also called scalar multiplication. An example of a scalar multiplication by multiplying K by P is given below in order to better understand this factor.

$$KP = P + P + P + P \dots + P$$

2. Elliptic Curve Discrete Logarithm Problem (ECDLP)

In the ECC cryptographic system, the computational problem of the discrete logarithm problem of an elliptic curve is abbreviated to ECDLP, which forms the basic block in the pairing-based and elliptic curve mechanism. Now if we have two points named P and Q on the surface of an elliptic curve, the point Q is the result of calculating the scalar multiplication of the value of K at the point P . Given the problem of discrete logarithms mentioned earlier, if we have two points P and Q , it is very difficult and even impossible to calculate the parameter k , even with those two parameters. In ECC encryption mechanism, this difficulty and impossibility of calculating the parameter is known as ECDLP or hard ellipse curve problem [14-15].

3. Delphi-Hellman ECDH Elliptic Curve

Other sub-theories of the ECC subset include Elliptic Curve Diffie–Hellman Key Exchange (ECDH), which is a method for key agreement between two entities based on anonymity. In this mechanism, each of the two communication parties has public and private keys based on the elliptic curve, which allows them to create their common session key or secrets in a secure name channel. Other sub-theories of the ECC subset include Elliptic Curve Diffie–Hellman Key Exchange (ECDH), which is a method for key agreement between two entities based on anonymity. In this mechanism, each of the two communication parties has public and private keys based on the elliptic curve, which allows them to create their common session key or secrets in a secure name channel. Consider the elliptic curve and assume that two points $p. a_i$ and $p. b_i$ are on the surface of this curve.

The Delphi-Hellmann Curve (ECDH) problem expresses the principle that if a resident on the network has access to these two points, It is impossible for he/she to reach bi (a_i, p) and ai (b_i, p).

B. RPL Overview

The Routing Protocol for low power and lossy networks (RPL) is an IPv6-based routing protocol. This protocol was developed by the IETF Group and can be identified as Routing Over Low Power and Lossy Networks (ROLL) [16]. The purpose of designing this protocol is to present it as a standard for low-consumption and lossless networks that can include all sensor nodes in an IoT network. RPL works by exploring routes by setting up an RPL network, hence it is considered an active routing protocol. This routing protocol forms a tree-like topology known as the destination non-cyclical directional graph (DODAG). In an RPL network, each node selects a parent based on predefined criteria, which acts as a gateway to that node. When a node intends to send a packet to its intended destination, it does not have a routing table for it. So, he has to pass that package to his parent who has a route to the next destination or transfer. This process continues until it reaches the final destination in the tree. One of the most important factors for an RPL is the choice of path, which uses several criteria for this purpose.³ traffic patterns can be mentioned for RPL packages. First, point-to-point (MP2P) traffic was sent from the leaves to the roots via upward paths. The second is point-to-point (P2MP) traffic from root to leaf using downward paths. Finally, the third pattern of point-to-point (P2P) traffic is represented by red dotted arrows using up and down paths.

Figure 1. Two instances of RPL network and three DODAG

C. RPL Security and challenges

Developing and implementing security in low-key networks and casualties is critical [17-18]. As mentioned earlier, the IoT network has resource constraints for many network nodes, which makes the implementation and deployment of security mechanisms in RPL very complex and difficult. In the routing process, RPL transmits information between network nodes, and many security challenges have been identified. IoT network nodes exchange packets for routing and addressing, which requires the definition of protocols and security mechanisms for routing packets being transmitted. These mechanisms and protocols must be compatible with different network topologies [19]. In general, RPL devices are vulnerable in nature due to their inability to resist tampering and allow network attackers to capture IoT nodes. In addition, it is possible to extract encrypted information and allow legal activity for an unauthorized node. An attacker with the ability to act as a network node tries to execute malicious code and try to change the routing rules. Each

network node is responsible for processing, which makes it effects [20]. In the routing process between nodes, there are potential threats and security issues that cause vulnerabilities that can endanger users' lives in cases such as human health monitoring devices [21]. As in any network, the protection and security of network data is very important, so in RPL routing, this is an important and challenging issue. A malicious node sends packets that are being transmitted across the network to carry out their unauthorized activities. This enables the malicious person or node to perform all kinds of attacks on the data being routed [22]. However, research shows that the standards defined for RPL protocol security are not able to meet the security challenges of the IoT network.

Usually, there are other security mechanisms in the link layer that are used in some infrastructures. The RPL standard for security has introduced three modes that can provide security features of message confidentiality and integrity.

Unsecure mode: In this case, the control messages sent by RPL are delivered without any security mechanism in the network. It is possible to adopt security requirements and mechanisms in another layer, such as the link layer.

Pre-installed mode: In this mode, any node that intends to join an RPL must have pre-defined keys. This is to ensure the security of RPL messages.

Authenticated Mode: This section is somewhat similar to the second mode, Pre-Installed. There are also pre-defined keys in this section, but with the difference that the keys are only for joining the RPL as a leaf node. The key can also be obtained from a central authentication reference.

Another security challenge in RPL is the large amount of information sent by network users, and the confidentiality of this data must be maintained. There are different encryption techniques to protect the privacy of users and the confidentiality of network users' information. These cryptographic systems are used for the purposes of user authentication, privacy and defense against a variety of network attacks. In addition, they provide conditions for the network that unauthorized persons are not able to operate and access network information. There are two techniques in order to use data encryption systems: symmetric and asymmetric encryption. The RPL protocol uses a symmetric encryption system to secure its data, which costs less than an asymmetric one. From the attack of symmetric encryption algorithms and standards, one can go to Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and Message Authentication Code (CBC-MAC Counter (CCM)) - (AES / CCM) pointed out. In an asymmetric encryption system, the two sides of the communication use a secret key that is already shared between them to encrypt the data. A common key is used for all nodes, which makes it easier for the network attacker to access. If an attacker on the network has access to secret keys under certain conditions, he/she can carry out his malicious actions on the network and even insert his malicious nodes into the network. In such a case, the network becomes vulnerable to all kinds of security attacks and the security and privacy of network nodes are compromised. Once the secret keys of the network are exposed to the network attackers, the cryptographic systems will no longer be able to protect the network [23-24]. As mentioned, research shows that RPL has experienced significant vulnerabilities, so improvements in security mechanisms and the RPL routing protocol authentication system are essential [25-26]. The routing protocol requires mechanisms for identifying inconsistencies, loop avoidance, validation, and detecting inconsistencies. Although the security requirements for RPL security have been provided by the IEFT, a valid security model has not been identified, which has posed challenges to the routing protocol security. The key management mechanism in RPL does not specify the characteristics, authentication and secure connection of nodes, which is a weakness in the design of the security standard. This design weakness makes the RPL protocol vulnerable to a variety of attacks [27]. Table 1 shows the types of routing attacks.

Table 1. Attacks on RPL protocol

Attack	Feature of the attach	Consequences on network's performance
Rank	Rank field and strict rank rules are exploited.	Generates routing loops. Increases end-to-end delay, PDR, control packet overhead, congestion, and energy consumption. Introduces unoptimized routes.
Spoofing/replaying Information	Create information or non-existent modify data partially	Attracting/repelling network traffic, creating routing loops.
Selective forwarding	Refusing massages to forward nodes from selected	Reducing traffic and increasing data loss
Blackhole	Failing data to forward its own packets any including	Reducing traffic and increasing data loss
Sniffing	Network traffic is eavesdropped for obtaining routing information from packets.	Introduces privacy concerns.
Sinkhole	Advertising false information to create a center of attraction for other nodes.	Compromise of transmission routes, reducing traffic and increase data loss.
Node replication	Physical capturing of node, its replication and deployment back into the network.	Compromise of transmission routes, eavesdropping on the falsely created links.
Jamming	Attacker transmit with high power radio signals to introduce heavy interference.	Decreases PDR and increases energy consumption.
Wormhole	Create a low link tunnel between two nodes in different parts of network	Sending data to the false distention, undermining cryptography protection.
Sybil	Single node contain multiple logical identity.	Overcomes voting schemes, compromises transmission routes by taking control of network.
Hello flood	Broadcasting packet to a the network with transmission power.	Increasing energy degradation and collisions, create false transmission routes.

Paper organization

Our goal in this paper is to focus on addressing the security challenges of the RPL protocol in routing nodes in the Internet of Things and providing a secure method of exchanging session keys as well as authentication of communication parties. The article is organized as follows. Related works are presented in the second section. Section III provides a proposed protocol for securing RPL. The security simulation results of the proposed protocol using the AVISPA network protocol review tool and the protocol resistance of the protocol against common network attacks are presented in Section IV. Section V compares the performance of the proposed protocol in terms of computational cost and also compares it with other protocols related to RPL and IoT security. Finally, the conclusion of the paper is reported in the section VI.

II. Related work

Security is very important in any network, and IoT routing also exchanges a significant amount of data. In addition, the security of nodes in the IoT is a critical issue. Due to the vulnerabilities of RPL and IoT, a lot of security research has been done.

In 2017, Airehrour et al. [28] proposed a trust-based routing protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks to identify Blackhole attacks and selective forwarding attacks. In the method provided by them, each node needs trust to operate and access the network, and the calculated value for each node is a criterion for parent

selection. In addition, their results show that the protocol provided by them does not incur additional costs on network traffic. In the same year, Tomić and McCann [29] presented their research on the deployment of WSN, in which the authors focused on key security mechanisms and their effects on WSN protocols and standards. They discuss personal networks, RPL routing protocols, potential security threats, and countermeasures that can be taken for threats at each layer. In addition, they have been simulated using Cooja to express the effects of attacks and network performance. In addition to the previous author Shrinovas et al. [30] Investigated the vulnerabilities of routing protocols for low-power networks. As a result of these investigations, they identified attacks in which the attacker's goal was to disrupt the RPL protocol routing process. The authors proposed a hacking system in 6LoWPAN networks with the aim of improving security. In addition, they have proposed the use of geographical hints to identify malicious nodes in an ETX-based network.

In 6LoWPAN networks, due to the need for low bandwidth and limited resources, the Internet Protocol version 6 and RPL are used in the wireless sensor network. RPL exchanges data without using an authentication mechanism, which leads to network disruption. An example is the Sinkhole attack. In 2018, Mahmoud et al. [31] examined these vulnerabilities and developed a hybrid monitoring method that aimed to detect abnormal behaviors in RPL-based networks. The model presented by them consists of two phases, in the first phase the information of the adjacent node is collected and in the second phase it is responsible for identifying the sink node. Different mechanisms and standards have been proposed for IoT security, and the centralized trust approach is one of the proposed mechanisms for security in this network. Therefore, Mehta et al. [32] proposed a trust mechanism based on trust to prevent the execution of Wormhole and Grayhole attack in the IoT network. Their proposed system has two approaches: direct and indirect trust, which uses the node properties in direct trust and in the indirect trust from the perspective of neighboring nodes. Features of this method are compatibility with RPL protocol in terms of energy consumption and low overhead in network traffic. Airehrour et al. [33] proposed a time-based trust model to protect the IoT network from routing attacks such as Rank and Sybil. This model provides a framework for IoT nodes that can exchange and communicate with each other on a trust basis. In the method proposed by the authors, the network environment is divided into smaller areas that help the network nodes to interact and trust.

One of the most challenging security issues is ensuring security in IoT routing protocols because the devices in this network are limited and heterogeneous resources. Hashemi et al. [34], due to limited resources for security, proposed a routing protocol that is participatory and based on conscious trust. In their proposed method, they have integrated a dynamic trust model with the RPL protocol that uses the required criteria and activities in combination to counter network security attacks. This combination of criteria was used to calculate the level of trust and help improve network performance. Moraly et al. [35] Focusing on the Sybil attack, which allows the adversary to compromise nodes and create illegitimate identities, they presented a Sybil attack modeling and a lightweight intrusion detection algorithm. They used artificial bee colonies for modeling, and their proposed algorithm has the ability to counter Sybil attack in the mobile RPL protocol. In their modeling, they have considered three different types of Sybil attack that are based on behavior. In addition, they examined the performance of RPL under attack with respect to packet delivery ratio factors, traffic control overhead, and power consumption. The Internet has provided a platform where a wide range of different devices and services can exchange information and provide different services with each other. However, the confidentiality of information and the lack of proper security requirements in the network cause numerous attacks that endanger the security of network users. Jain, Akanksha, and Sweta Jain [36] have examined traditional methods of routing security in terms of factors such as limitations, secure routing problems, and existing techniques.

The IPv6-based RPL protocol uses DODAG (DIO) information object object to propagate routing information between RPL network nodes. A malicious node can access these messages by eavesdropping and sending them over and over again at different times on the network. Verma A, Ranga V [37] introduced an

intrusion detection system called CoSec-RPL to prevent this attack. A non-fake copy attack can significantly increase the average delay and packet delivery on the network. But the authors show that their proposed method is not only resistant to attacks, but can also effectively reduce network power consumption and add overhead to nodes. Due to the compactness of the 6LoWPAN and RPL protocols, several attacks, including wormhole, blackhole, sinkhole, sybil, rank, selective forwarding, and various denial of service attacks, put them at risk. V. Neerugatti et al. [38] proposed a multi-diagnostic scheme to secure these protocols and reduce attacks. The proposed design is based on artificial intelligence, which used the ContikiCooja simulator implemented with Sky motes to implement its design. Patel et al. [39] focus on selective transmission attack and increase the security of the RPL protocol by providing a method in which a reputation-based mechanism is embedded in the RPL routing protocol. The reputation criterion in the method presented by them is calculated by evaluating the behavior of the node in the Internet of Things. This behavior is based on sending node data in the network, which evaluates the actual and estimated number of lost packets. The calculated reputation value is used to select the parent in the network. IoT network security is an important issue and due to the scalability of this network, so-called security mechanisms such as encryption techniques, key management, intrusion detection system, anomaly detection have many challenges to implement. Prathapchandran et al. [40] Using the trust mechanism, they presented a lightweight approach that can be effective in ensuring IoT security. In their method of targeting network malicious nodes, they have used random forest (RF) and mental logic (SL). Agiollo, Andrea, et al. [41] Introduced an intrusion detection system (IDS) to reduce RPL overhead and energy consumption. Their proposed method, called DETONAR - Detector of Routing Attacks in RPL, uses a combination of signature and expression anomalies to detect illegal behavior in the network. In addition, they used RADAR - Routing Attacks Dataset for RPL to evaluate their intrusion detection system.

III. Proposed schema

Numerous studies have been conducted on the security of the RPL and network routing protocols as well as the IoT, and have shown that weak devices with limited resources have created many security problems for the IoT network and the network routing protocol. As mentioned in the previous sections, RPL has a vulnerable nature that provides the right conditions for all types of network attacks. One of the most important issues that has weakened this routing protocol is the lack of authentication mechanism and the use of symmetric encryption for the entire network.

In this part of the article, we present a robust authentication protocol with a key exchange mechanism to secure the RPL protocol based on our RPL security reviews. In our proposed method, we have used ECC techniques and theories that are compatible with the resource quality of weak IoT devices. The proposed method consists of two phases, the registration phase in which each node must be entered by a node to enter the network. Do parent or Root. This phase verifies the authorized identity of each network node.

The second phase, which is authentication and key exchange, is a process for this phase in which two related entities, in addition to being able to generate different encryption keys for each session, authenticate each other with private parameters. Table 2 explains the definition of the parameters used in the proposed protocol.

Table 2 describes the parameters used in the proposed protocol.

Symbol	Definition
ID	Nod Identity

PU	Public Key
PV	Private Key
$d_i, f_i, e_i, a_i, b_i, g_i, c_i, z_i, l_i$	Random Numbers
H	Hash Function
P	Base Point
AC	Authentication Certificate
SK	Session Key
E	Encrypt by Symmetric Key

A. Registration phase

The first step of the proposed protocol is the registration phase, in which any node intending to enter the network must do at least one of these steps. If a node is completely out of the network for a long time, it must also go through the registration phase again to enter the network. In the first step, the node selects two random numbers c_i and l_i . The next step produces the value N_i , which is an anonymous type of node private key. The reason for producing this parameter is that it is used in generating the Authentication Certificate parameter and is a step of authentication based on the private parameters of both parties to the entity. In addition, it helps the protocol to withstand Forgery of identity attacks.

$$N_i = H((PV_{\text{node}} * c_i) || l_i)$$

In the last step of this phase, the node sends the value N to Root with its public key.

Root selects the random numbers a_i and b_i in the first step after receiving the parameters sent by the node. After selecting random numbers, it generates an anomaly from its private key, which stores its value in T_i . This technique of generating anonymity from the private keys of communication institutions helps us, in addition to using the features of private keys, to maintain their security in the absence of disclosure and accessibility of network attackers. In the next step, the Root entity generates an authentication certificate for the node using its private parameters and the node (N_i and T_i). This certificate is for nodes only and this value is different for each node because it uses the private key of each node in its production. Figure 2 illustrate the registration process and the values used in the registration process.

Registration Phase

NODE

ROOT

Select Random number c_i, l_i

$$N_i = H((PV_{node} * c_i) || l_i)$$

ID_i, PU_{node}

Select Random number a_i, b_i

$$T_i = H((PV_{Root} * a_i) || b_i)$$

$$AC = H(T_i || ID_{Node} || N_i)$$

Select A Symmetric Key

$AC, \text{Symmetric Key}$

Figure 2. Registration phase

B. Authentication and key exchange phase

In this stage, which includes 3 steps, the communication parties exchange parameters in order to authenticate each other and securely generate the Session key.

Step 1:

In the proposed protocol is the start of communication with the node. For this purpose, the node first generates random numbers d_i, e_i and f_i . The next step is to use node private parameters to authenticate as well as prevent attackers from forging attacks. For this operation, we use the private key of the node. But for the security of the private key, it should not be used directly in the production of parameters, and therefore we use anonymity techniques or generate a root of the private key. To implement this technique, we used a combination of random numbers and a private key. The parameter U_i is the result of this combination, which is calculated as follows.

$$U_i = H((PV_{node} * d_i) || e_i)$$

In the third action of this step, the node produces parameter A, which is the product of the scalar multiplication of the random number f and the base point. This parameter is used in generating the session key and is also effective in the protocol authentication mechanism. After generating parameter A, we need to create a multiple authentication mechanism as well as a process to ensure the accuracy of the values received on the root side, and for this purpose we generate parameter S as follows.

$$S = H(AC || U_i || A)$$

At the end of the node, it encrypts the parameters S, A, and U_i with the symmetric key received from Root during the registration step and sends them to the Root entity.

Step 2:

In this step, the Root entity receives the encrypted message by the node, which carries the parameters S , A , and U_i . The first step, Root examining the freshness of the message by calculating the value of ΔT . Checking the freshness of the message is done in order to prevent Send repetitive messages and reply attacks. After checking the freshness of the message, it is necessary to check the node identity and its sent parameters. For this purpose, Root calculates the value of S' and compares it with the parameter S sent by the node. Any changes in the parameters will cause a non-equality of the parameter calculated by the root and the value received from the node, which mismatch is a reason for disconnection between communication entities. If the values are equal, which means the information is correct, the root will continue the protocol process. After verifying the information, Root selects a random number g and generates the session key as follows.

$$SK = H(AC \parallel S \parallel R \parallel g_i \cdot A)$$

After calculating the session key, the Root entity generates an R value to authenticate itself and verify the sent parameters by the node. Finally, it sends a message encrypted with a symmetric key that contains the parameters R and $g_i \cdot p$ to the node.

$$R = H(S \parallel SK \parallel AC)$$

Note: The values A and $g_i \cdot p$ play a role in generating the session key and these points are sent encrypted in the channel. But it is noteworthy that if under certain conditions the network symmetric key is exposed and the points A and $g_i \cdot p$ are in the possession of the attacker, according to the ECDH theorem described in the concepts section, it will not be possible to calculate $g_i \cdot f_i \cdot p$. In addition, these points play an important role in the identification of entities.

Step 3:

This is the last step in the authentication and key agreement process. The node first examines the freshness of the message by calculating ΔT . If not new, disconnect. The next step for the node is to authenticate the Root node and its submitted parameters. For these operations, it first generates the session key node and calculates the value of R' after generating the session key. How to calculate the parameters is as follows.

$$SK' = H(AC \parallel S \parallel R \parallel g_i \cdot f_i \cdot p)$$

$$R' = H(S \parallel SK' \parallel AC)$$

The parameter AC , which is generated for the node at the registration stage, and S , which is generated by the node itself. The node generates the session key using the parameters it has and is sent by Root, and then generates the R' parameter. Now it is time to check the accuracy of the parameters and root authentication, which is done by checking the two values of R' and R . If these two values are equal, it means that the information sent is correct and the sender of the information is Root, otherwise the connection will be lost. Finally, by confirming the accuracy of the information, the value of the generated SK is selected as the session key. Figure 3 shows the authentication process and key-agreement process of the proposed schema.

Authentication and Key Agreement Phase

Figure 3. Authentication and key agreement phase

IV. Security analysis of the proposed scheme

In this part of the article, we have reviewed the security of our proposed method, which we have formally and informally evaluated. To prove the security of the private parameters used in the protocol, as well as the types of active and passive network attacks, we have implemented the proposed protocol with the official AVISPA tool, which is to check the security of the protocol. In addition, in the informal analysis section, we introduce the common types of network attacks and state that the proposed protocol is safe against these attacks.

A. Informal review of the proposed protocol security

Reply attack

This attack can be introduced as one of the most common network attacks. In this attack, the adversary reaches the messages and packets sent on the network and steals them for himself. It then sends these packets frequently over the network at other times. This iteration and delay that occurs in sending can be done by the sender or network nodes. In the proposed protocol to prevent this attack, two factors are considered to check the novelty of the message and random numbers. As stated in the protocol process description section, communication entities first send a message with the value $Receives \Delta T = |T_2 - T_1|$ examine. If the incoming message is not fresh, the connection will be lost. In addition, the random numbers used to generate the parameters make a difference in each session, which prevents the duplication of messages and parameters.

Impersonation Attack

This attack helps the adversary in the network to identify itself as an authorized node and to be able to communicate with other nodes in the network. In order to prevent this attack, we have used multiple authentication mechanisms and private parameters in the proposed protocol. For multiple authentication, we have considered the S and R parameters, which are used by both parties to the authentication. In addition, in the registration section, we have considered the AC parameter, which is unique to each authentication node and is used in the production of authentication parameters and session keys. It is important to note that the AC parameter is never sent to the channel during the phase-authentication and key exchange process. The strongest parameter we have considered for authentication is points A and g_i , p, which according to the ECDH theorem, it is not possible to reach the session key even with the exposure of points. Because they are in calculable and the correct calculation of the session key can only be done by an authenticated and authorized entity.

Perfect Forward Secrecy

This security feature is very important in authentication and key agreement protocols, and every protocol must have this feature to be able to protect session keys and private parameters. In addition, the Perfect Forward Secrecy feature creates different session keys with no connection between the keys of each session. In the proposed method, random numbers are used to implement this feature and create conditions for generating parameters whose value in each session is different from the previous session. This factor helps the protocol to generate the session keys in each entity relationship that are completely different and independent.

Selective Forwarding Attack

This attack is one of the common attacks of RPL routing protocol, attacker captured the sent packets in the network and resends them selectively. The first security factor needed to prevent this is the authentication mechanism to prevent malicious nodes from operating on the network. As previously described, the proposed protocol is implemented by a multiple authentication mechanism. But certain circumstances may arise where an attacker has the opportunity to send a message on the network and intend to implement a Selective Forwarding Attack on the network. The protocol presented in each step first examines the freshness of the message and also uses random numbers in the protocol process. Therefore, it allows communication entities to identify duplicate and outdated messages and disconnect them.

Secure against the DOS attack

This attack helps the attacker to send repeated and consecutive messages on the network or a specific node. The purpose of this attack is to disable the network, reduce performance and cause latency in the network. If an attacker on the network sends duplicate messages or sends a large number of messages, due to the use of random numbers as well as the time stamp of the recipient of the message, it checks the freshness of the messages and recognizes their duplication. As a result, it will disconnect.

B. Result and Formal Analyze

In this section, we have formally analyzed our proposed method. To formally check security, we have used AVISPA software, which is a reliable tool for evaluating security and analyzing Internet security protocols. It uses an automated security analysis system and esoteric servers such as On-the-Fly Modeler (OFMC) and Constraint-Logic (Cl-AtSe). In addition, AVISPA has the ability to evaluate protocols under various attacks. Given the capabilities of this software, we decided to use the AVISPA tool to check the security of our protocol against all kinds of attacks and the confidentiality of private values [42]. Figure 4 shows the results of security checks on the AVISPA tool.

Figure 4. AVISPA results. (a) OFMC (b) ATSE

The formal evaluation and the results of Figure 4 show that the proposed method has the ability to resist all types of active and passive network attacks. The AVISPA tool has two outputs, OFMC and CL-ATSE, which indicate that the private parameters used in the protocol are protected and cannot be accessed and calculated by network attackers.

V. Performance evaluation

As mentioned in the previous sections, IoT network nodes have limited resources, so RPL requires a security mechanism that has less computational cost. In this section we have calculated the time complexity of the proposed method for the authentication and key exchange process. In addition in Table 4, we have compared our proposed protocol with other IoT network security protocols in terms of computational cost. In order to implement the results, a system with a 2.20 GHz Intel Pentium E2200 processor, 2 GB of RAM is considered. According to the report in [43-44] the time of performing different operations for each cryptographic element is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Execution time of cryptographic elements.

Notation	Description	Time cost (ms)
T_H	Time for a general hash operation	≈ 0.0023
T_{SE}	Time for a symmetric encryption/decryption	≈ 0.0046
T_{AE}	Time for an asymmetric encryption/decryption	≈ 3.85
T_E	Time for an exponentiation	≈ 3.85
T_M	Time for an EC point multiplication	≈ 2.226
T_A	Time for an EC point addition	≈ 0.0288
T_P	Time for a bilinear pairing	≈ 5.811
T_{HM}	Time for an HMAC operation	≈ 0.0046

Table 4 Extensive comparison of the related protocols.

Computations	Computational cost (ms)	
Ashok Kumar, et al. [45]	$7T_M + 6T_H + 3T_A$	15.6822
Ming, et al [46]	$3T_M + 4T_P + 4T_H + T_A$	29.96
Li, Fagen [47]	$3T_M + 5T_P + 2T_H + 2T_A$	35.7952
Majumder. et al. [48]	$5T_H + 6T_M + 4T_{SE}$	13.3859
Dey, S. and Hossain, A [49]	$6T_H + 4T_E + 6T_{SE}$	15.41656
Gupta, Daya Sagar, et al. [50]	$3T_M + 2T_P$	18.3
Safkhani, Masoumeh, et al.[51]	$9T_M + 10T_H$	20.057
Proposed Protocol	$3T_M + 7T_H + 2T_{Se}$	6.703

The results of the data in Table 4, which compares our proposed protocol with other IoT protocols in terms of computational cost, show that our proposed method has much less time than other protocols. Due to the fact that IoT network nodes have limited resources and less power, they need security mechanisms that do not spend a lot of energy when calculating protocol operations when routing by RPL protocol. Therefore, our proposed method, which takes less computation time to perform authentication and key agreement operations, is more suitable and compatible for RPL network nodes.

VI. Conclusion

The Internet of Things is a global infrastructure that supports a variety of standard communication protocols. In addition, its features and capabilities provide the conditions for its use in a wide range of services. Examples include healthcare, smart cities, smart homes, and industrial environments. This breadth of services has made the network an important target for network attackers. On the other hand, resource and computational constraints have created vulnerabilities for some elements of this network, most of which can be seen in the Routing Protocol (RPL). In this article, we tried to address the security challenges and vulnerabilities of IoT, especially RPL. Finally, we proposed a scheme to cover RPL vulnerabilities under limited node conditions. Formal and informal reviews that assessed the security of the proposed method show that the proposed protocol has been able to provide security against a variety of network attacks and cover RPL vulnerabilities. In addition, due to the low energy of RPL nodes, the proposed protocol had the lowest computational time compared to other proposed protocols.

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